

Effect of Conceptual Understanding of Mathematical Principles on Academic Achievement of Secondary Level Chemistry Students

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Abstract

The study aimed at to investigate the understanding of Mathematical principles and achievement of students at secondary level in the subject of Chemistry. Quasi-experimental design was adopted for this study. Pre-test and post-test were used. Two existing groups (intact groups) comprising 45 students each were selected as a sample and named experimental group-1 & experimental group-2 respectively. Third group was control group. Intact groups were selected. All groups were equated by an achievement test. The achievement test was developed on the selected topics of basic Mathematics and Chemistry textbook concepts at the secondary level; that were to be taught during the treatment period of research. The research tool was validated by experts. The experimental groups were taught the principles of Mathematics that are used in Chemistry concepts like mole ratios, Avogadro's number, molarity calculations, etc. The Control group was given treatment of same concepts by the traditional method. After treatment, the post-test was conducted and data was collected. The t-test was used as statistical tool for finding the mean differences between groups. It was found from results that performance of the students in experimental groups was better than the performance of students in control group on the post-test. It was also found that the teaching of relevant Mathematics principles before the teaching of Chemistry is more effective than teaching Chemistry by traditional method. It is recommended that the relevant Mathematics principles must be taught before the teaching Chemistry concepts like mole ratios, Avogadro's number, molarity, and gas laws etc. The study is significant because the finding of this study will facilitate to find out whether Mathematics knowledge has any effect on learners' performance in Chemistry. The information will be helpful for the curriculum planner to create links between Chemistry and Mathematics curriculum and to include more applied Mathematics in the curriculum. The researcher intends to be able to provide workable suggestions or recommendations because Mathematical skills have a great effect on all the science and social science subjects. Lot of students faced problems in solving conceptual numerical in the subject of chemistry due to lack of Mathematical skills. The finding of this study will also help the other science teachers to adopt the methods or strategies for making students more convenient to solve the numerical problems or derivations in the subject of Chemistry

Introduction

The Chemistry Curriculum for grades IX through XII is based upon the principle of vertical progression routed from the basic subject of the science of 8th grade. Chemistry as an independent science is being offered by this curriculum now at this stage at the secondary level. It highlights the content, problem-solving, inquiry, process skills, and critical and analytical skills of thinking. The Chemistry curriculum offers a radical shift from the traditional curriculum (available at <http://www.mofept.gov.pk>). With the rapid knowledge explosion in the field of science, the role of research has been increasing especially for the subject of Chemistry. The interaction among different science subjects has been increasing over time. The requirement of knowing connected subjects has enhanced because of the numerous applications of Chemistry. The knowledge of Chemistry provides the base for all-natural science subjects. Mathematics is the basic science that is necessary for many other fields to understand. Probably, there is no subject like Mathematics that forms a joining force among the social sciences and different branches of science (Offiah, 2012). The subject of Mathematics is considered the mother of science subjects and basic source of skills and information for technological societies. It is because the concepts and principles in mathematics help learning of other science subjects (Manapure, March 2011).

Constructivist Approaches to Teaching Science

Constructivist theories of learning stress learners' active interaction with his or her environment, the importance of peer learning, and problem-solving to develop higher-order cognitive skills. Cooperative and collaborative learning approaches, inquiry approach, discovery method, problem-solving and project method are a few of the most frequently cited examples of constructivist approaches and methods of teaching science.

Science and Mathematics Education in Pakistan

The educational system of Pakistan consists of basic and higher education. Primary, elementary and secondary constitute the levels of basic education while higher secondary and graduate levels are considered higher education. The subject of Science is compulsory at primary and elementary levels. However, in grades I, II, and III, science is taught as integrated science as 'General Knowledge'. From grade four to eight General science is taught. Science subjects like Physics, Chemistry, Biology and General Science are elective subjects at secondary school level in Pakistan. Total time of study science at primary level is 12%, at elementary level is 13 to 14 %. Whereas a large proportion of study time has been allocated for study of science subjects. Physics, Chemistry, Biology/ Computer Science and Mathematics are placed in Science group. At the secondary school level, twelve to fourteen percent

(12 to 14%) of school time is allowed for each science subject. The students who performed well in the subjects of Mathematics and Science in class VIII have the opportunity to opt for the science group. (Halai, Razvi, & Rodrigues, 2007). In Pakistan, in 1959, Science Education Commission (SEC) was established which recommended being made science education compulsory for middle (VI-VIII) classes. In between 1950 and 1960 education of science was made compulsory for middle classes but its quality was not good (Iqbal & Mahmood, 2000). In the 1979 education policy of Pakistan, a recommendation was made for the promotion of science education. For this purpose, a Science Education Project (SEP) was started in 1984 (Hill & Tanveer, 1990). According to Iqbal & Mahmood (2000) in various educational policies (1972 to 1998-2010) the emphasis has been made on science education and technical education. (Iqbal & Mahmood, 2000).

Mathematics and Science Teachers in Pakistan

Teachers' role in implementing changing science and Mathematics curriculum cannot be ignored. The profile of Science and Mathematics teachers in Pakistan was not known and documented through researches. Despite the lack of researches on documentation of data on teachers' qualifications and their subject specialization, there is substantial evidence to suggest that there was a dearth of science and mathematics teachers in the country (National Educational Policy, Govt. of Pakistan, 1998 - 2010). The NEP 1998-2010 makes clear these issues as "there is no school in Pakistan, where there is no vacant post of science teacher, hence it is assumed that there is a shortage of Science teachers in Pakistan." The situation about female secondary schools as indicated in the national document is even worse. There is a deficiency of instructors in Mathematics and science to understand the reasons for this shortage one can go through the policy regarding the recruitment and appointment of teachers. These recruitment policies indicate that budget neither allocated nor has been given advertisement for these separate designated posts (HassanAly, 2006). According to Hassan Aly, the country has about 203 teaching training institutions. Besides these centers, 300 other teachers' resource centers were working up to 2006 under the Education Sector Reform program. (HassanAly, 2006). AIOU awards a very huge number of Bachelors of education degrees through its distance learning program. Instructors from far-flung areas are awardees of these degrees. The Matriculation with a primary teaching certificate, intermediate with a certificate of teaching (CT) and Bachelor or Master degree with Bachelor of education for primary, middle and secondary schools' teachers respectively. (Pakistan, 1998-2010, p.21). For the sake of in-service teachers' development, there are no obvious policies and facilities. Some private educational institutions have worked in this regard. According to 1998-2010 policy throughout the country trained teachers are appointed as senior and junior school teachers (Govt. of Pakistan, 1998-2010, p.38). It was identified that Science and Mathematics subjects are taught by untrained teachers. As a result it was acknowledged in National Education Policy, 1998-2010 that teachers had very few chances to interact with subject specialist teachers and peers of the respective subject (Govt. of Pakistan, 1998-2010, p. 49). The annually published Pakistan School Education Statistics is available up to 2011-2012 which indicates the numbers of school teachers of different levels but it does not point out the number of science teachers. However, data classified as F. Sc, B. Sc, and M. Sc qualification bases found in School Education Statistics

(2000-2001 helped to infer the number of science teachers present in Punjab province while such classified data of other provinces is not available.

Importance of Mathematics

Mathematics was and has become a vital factor for development in every field of life. It can be assumed that there is no scientific study which can be done without mathematics. The application of mathematical concepts, principles and understanding starts at very early age of every person. Mathematical principles and formulae used at early classes provide a baseline foundation for higher level studies. The success of life is more concerned with the knowledge and understanding of mathematics (Pandey, 2017)

Understanding of Mathematics is equally significant for us because of its variety of uses in business, work, and finance; and for personal decision-making cannot be denied. For understanding science, technology, engineering, and economics, the subject of Mathematics provides tools for the proper comprehension of these subjects. The knowledge of Mathematics is important for rational decision-making to boost up the economy at the national level. Mathematics is the subject that enables the students to explain, alter and analyze the planet. It creates moments of enjoyment and marvel for all students once they get some solution, finds an answer, or hidden links. Mathematics may be, an artistic field. The language of Mathematics is considered universal. Its importance is internationally accepted and has no cultural boundaries. Mathematics has gained this place over a long period as a method of determining issues and additionally for its own sake. In 'Al-Muqaddimah' Ibn Khaldun stresses the role of Mathematics. He says that the beginning of education should be made with Mathematics. It is Mathematics that develops well-designed brains. Those who have studied Mathematics in their childhood are trustworthy. It is because they have developed solid bases for reasoning that has become their second nature. (Gouba, 2008). Mathematics Subject is the science of calculations, formulae, order, structure, and relationship that has originated from measuring, counting, and describing the forms and shapes of different objects. Its concern is with quantitative calculation and reasoning logically. Life cannot be led without Mathematics because neither can we count nor anything else without Mathematics (Encyclopedia, 2009).

Effect of Mathematics on Other Subjects

Mathematics is considered the queen of all sciences. . It is necessary to understand many fields. University of Northern British Columbia has mentioned a list of subjects like Chemistry, biology, physics, engineering, psychology, nursing; pharmacy, anthropology, optometry, communications, linguistics, commerce, economics, education, geography, networking, software development, computer science, Business, actuarial science (used by insurance companies) and medicine required a good knowledge of Mathematics and statistics.

Every field of Mathematics has its specific applications to a different career. For example, the study of symmetry in Chemistry and Physics Algebra for computer science, networking, and cryptology. Calculus in the form of a differential equation is applied in Chemistry, Physics, Biology, hydrodynamics, Engineering, rocket science, option price modeling in Business, molecular structure, and Economics models, etc. (Columbia, 2012)

Setidisho declared in 1996 that Mathematics is a binding force that joins all the science subjects together (Setidisho, 1996). Odeyeni in 1995 said that "Mathematics was a scientific language and main intellectual discipline of sciences for technological development" (Odeyemi, 1995). Many types of researches were conducted to see the effect of Mathematics on other subjects like Biology, physics.

Relationship between Mathematics and Chemistry

Throughout the nations, Mathematics and Science have prime importance due to several advantages obtained from them. There is a general agreement that Mathematics is the foundation of science as well as technology. Hence Mathematics education is considered essential for sustained development and growth of science and technology (Udousoro, 2011). Despite the importance attached to the study of Mathematics at all levels of education, it is the most feared by the learners from primary to tertiary levels of education (Kramers-pals, Lambrechts, & Wolff, 2000).

The links between Mathematics and Chemistry is the use of ratio, proportions, graphical analysis, geometry, and logarithms. Most high school students will have completed at least an introductory overview of all of these concepts by their sophomore year. However, upper-level high school and even college Chemistry students consistently report that the difficulty of the underlying Mathematics is a significant cause of difficulty with the subject (Bradeen, et al., 1998) .

Udousoro (2011) a study was conducted on senior secondary Chemistry curriculum in Nigeria and West African from senior certificate syllabus. This research revealed that to understand Mathematical concepts on formula, isotopy, molar ratio, equations, quantitative, chemical-kinetics, laws of chemical equilibria, PH radioactivity, solubility, etc in Chemistry, involve a lot of computational areas, hence requires a sound knowledge of basic Mathematics (Udousoro, 2011). Oluwatayo (2011) has quoted a large number of studies that have determined the relationship of Mathematics with Chemistry. Findings of these studies, according to Oluwatayo (2011), have established that Mathematics provides the foundations for the understanding of concepts of Chemistry (Oluwatayo, 2011). Oluwatayo (2011) has also pointed out that many students considered Chemistry as a difficult subject because it contains a Mathematical skills and its nature is abstract. (Oluwatayo, 2011)

Purpose of the Study

Mathematics education had been identified as one of the great problems for students' performance in Chemistry. In the subject of chemistry for IX-X grade, many concepts of Mathematics are used. The command of those mathematical basic principles and concepts is a pre-requisite for a thorough understanding of Chemistry taught at the same level of education. It has been the prominent problem addressed in this study that what is the suitable time to introduce Mathematical principles coinciding with the subject of Chemistry.

The purpose of this study was to find out the effect of mathematical principles on the achievement of Chemistry and compare the performance of the experimental groups; the group that was taught Mathematics before the teaching of Chemistry, and the control group.

Methodology

This study followed one of the Quasi-experimental designs named as 'Pre-test Post-test Control group'. In this design generally, three existing groups (intact groups) were pre-tested, administered treatment to one group, which is the experimental group, and post-tested. I chose Quasi-Experimental Design. One control group and two experimental groups were used. The design of the study may be represented as:

	$E_1 =$	O_1	X	O_2
	$E_2 =$	O_3	X	O_4
	$C =$	O_5	$-$	O_6

Where

E = Experimental groups

C = Control group

$O_1, O_3, \& O_5$ = Pre-tests

$O_2, O_4, \& O_6$ = Post-tests

Experimental Groups: Students who were taught simple Mathematics principles before and during the time when chemistry was taught.

Control Group: The Students in this group were taught only Chemistry without special Mathematical treatment.

Sample The study was conducted in Islamabad Model College for Boys in Islamabad Capital Territory, Pakistan. There were seven sections (A to G) in the college. The experimental and control groups were selected randomly by draw method from seven sections. The research sample consisted of 90 students, 45 students of each class. Class / Section "A" was designated the control group while section "C" was assigned as Experimental Group-I and section "D" was assigned as Experimental Group-II.

Instrument

The data collection tool was CAT (Chemistry Achievement Test) based on simple Mathematics principles. Tool comprises concepts of chemistry based on mathematical calculations, derivations and uses of formulae. The level of chemistry was 9th Grade curriculum for Secondary School Chemistry including topics of electrolysis, Avogadro s' number, energy and chemical reaction, oxidation state/number calculation, mole, and calculation on gas laws. Initially, 40 MCQs test items were prepared. The test was first reviewed by the six subject specialists, three of Chemistry and three of Mathematics for content validity. As a result of content validity by experts. Ten items were discarded as a result of pilot testing. Then this test was administered to 15 students of another college of the same level for which it was going to be administered. After this, the test attained the final shape. 15 MCQ were based on simple basic Mathematics and 15 MCQs were based on Chemistry test items utilizing these simple Mathematics principles. Each question stem had plausible distracters. To make the test items more reliable four distracters were used.

Three groups in this study were selected by the random draw method before treatment started. Two types of interventions were undertaken. Before first intervention took place mathematical concepts and Chemistry concepts were mapped. The first treatment was the Mathematics teaching referred to as the Simple basic Mathematics Principles (SMPs) that were included scientific notation, significant digits, unit analysis, and a problem-solving technique. These Mathematical concepts were taught through the following topics: simple equations, significant figures, statistical treatment of data, change of subject formula, and measurement. The second teaching treatment was Chemistry teaching. Important topics which were assumed to be taught in a better way with the help of mathematical principles were electrolysis, Avogadro s' number, energy and chemical reaction, oxidation state/number calculation, mole, and calculation on gas laws. All three groups were given a pre-test before commencing the experiment. This intervention lasted for four weeks.

Experimental Groups

During the first two weeks, these groups were taught Simple Mathematics principles using 5 periods per week of 40 minutes each. In third and fourth week, Chemistry was taught to the experimental group students by the Chemistry teacher. In these two weeks 5 periods of 40 minutes duration was used. First mathematics was taught and after this Chemistry was taught. Periods of mathematics and chemistry were consecutive. Thus Chemistry was taught alongside Mathematics.

Control Group

This group was not taught Simple Mathematics principles. From the third week to the fourth week, this group was taught Mathematics and Chemistry by the traditional way as is present in the college timetable at five periods per week. When treatment time was finished all students were given three days time for review. Now post-test was administered for each group. The test was the same which was administered in the pre-test to study.

Analysis of Data and Findings

Table 1

Comparison of the performance with respect to mean scores among Control Group and the first Experimental Group in the subject of Mathematics on pre-test. (N=90)

Groups	First Experimental Group	Control Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	5.84	5.276	88	1.147**
SD	2.576	2.189		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 1, the values of $\bar{x}=5.84$ for first experimental group and $\bar{x}=5.276$ value for control group. Tabular value of t is 1.9873* where as calculated value is 1.147**. Almost no difference between first experimental group and control group existed.

Table 2

Comparison of the performance with respect to mean scores among Control Group and the first Experimental Group in the subject of Chemistry on pre-test. (N=90)

Groups	First Experimental Group	Control Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	3.36	3.42	88	0.188**
SD	1.612	1.751		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 2, the values of $\bar{x}=3.36$ for first experimental group and $\bar{x}=3.42$ for control group. Tabulated value of t is 1.9873* whereas calculated value of t is 0.188**. Mean values of both first experimental group and Control group are very close to each other on pre test. This means that performance of both groups is almost same.

Table 3

Overall comparison of mean scores of the subjects of Mathematics and Chemistry between control group and first experimental group (N=90)

Groups	Experimental Group I	Control Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	9.20	9.56	88	0.589**
SD	3.181	2.510		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 3, the values of $\bar{x}=9.20$ for first experimental group and $\bar{x}=9.56$ for control group. As shown in the table 3 calculated value of t (0.589**) < (1.9873*) at a significance level of 0.05.

Very close mean values of both first experimental group and control group shows that performance of both groups is same on pre test in both subjects.

Table 4

Comparison of Pre-test mean scores of the Control Group and the second Experimental Group in the subject of Mathematics (N=90)

Groups	Second Experimental Group	Control Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	5.31	5.27	88	0.107**
SD	1.743	2.189		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 4, the values of $\bar{x}=5.31$ for second experimental group and $\bar{x}=5.27$ for control group is very close to each other. Calculated the value of t 0.107* < 1.9873**. As Table value is less than calculated value in the subject of Mathematics.

Table 5

Comparison of mean scores of the Control Group and the second Experimental Group on pre-test in the subject of Chemistry (N=90)

Groups	Second Experimental Group	Control Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	3.47	3.42	88	0.120**
SD	1.753	1.751		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 4, the values of \bar{x} =3.41 for second experimental group and \bar{x} =3.42 for control group on pre-test are very close to each other. Calculated value (0.120*) is smaller than tabulated value (1.9873**) among control group and experimental group-II on pre test bject of Chemistry.

Table 6

Overall comparison of mean scores of the subjects of Mathematics and Chemistry between control group and second experimental group (N=90)

Groups	Second Experimental Group	Control Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	9.09	9.56	88	0.901**
SD	2.401	2.510		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 6, the values of \bar{x} =9.09 for second experimental group and \bar{x} =9.56 for control group are somewhat close to each other for both groups on pre-test in both subjects. Calculated value of t (0. .901) < (1.9873) at the significance of the level of 0.05.

Table 7

Comparison regarding Performance of the first Experimental Group and second Experimental Group on Pre-test in the subject of Mathematics (N=90)

Groups	First Experimental Group	Second Experimental Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	5.84	5.31	88	1.150**
SD	2.576	1.743		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 7, the values of \bar{x} =5.84 for first experimental group and \bar{x} = 5.31 for second experimental group depicts that there was no statistically significant difference between the above two groups concerning pre-test mean scores in the subject of Mathematics The result drawn is that the pre-test performance of both groups is almost same at the same level.

Table 8

Comparison on the Performance of the Experimental Group I and Experimental Group II on Pre-test in the subject of Chemistry (N=90)

Groups	First Experimental Group	Second Experimental Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	3.36	3.47	88	0.313**
SD	1.612	1.753		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 8, the values of \bar{x} =3.36 for first experimental group and \bar{x} = 3.47 for second experimental group. Values 3.36 and 3.47 are almost same. Further tabulated value of t 0.313 * is smaller than calculated value of t 1.9873** for first experimental group and second experimental group.

Table 9

Comparison of Performance of first Experimental Group and second Experimental Group on Pre-test as a Whole test (overall) (N=90)

Groups	First Experimental Group	Second Experimental Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	9.20	9.09	88	0.187**
SD	2.576	2.189		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 8, the values of \bar{x} =9.20 for first experimental group and \bar{x} = 9.09 for second experimental group. Further Table 9 shows that the calculated value of t (0.187) < (1.9873) at a significance of the level of 0.05. The above values depict that there is almost no difference between the overall performance of both groups on pretest as a whole in both subjects of Chemistry and Mathematics. It is clear from the data presented and analyzed in Table No. 1 to 9 that both the experimental and control groups were almost equal on the pre-test in Mathematics, Chemistry as well as overall on the pre-test.

Table 10

Comparison of Post-test mean scores of the Control Group and the first Experimental Group in the subject of Mathematics (N=90)

Groups	First Experimental Group	Control Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	12.00	9.76	88	5.479**
SD	1.907	1.979		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 10, the values of $\bar{x}=12.00$ for first experimental group and $\bar{x}=9.76$ for control group. Further tabulated t value 1.9873* is smaller than calculated t value 5.479**. It depicted that there is a statistically significant difference between the above two groups concerning post-test mean scores in the subject of mathematics. This difference was due to intervention provided to the first experimental group students.

Table 11

Comparison of Post-test mean scores of the Control Group and the first Experimental Group in the subject of Chemistry (N=90)

Groups	First Experimental Group	Control Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	11.13	8.18	88	7.378**
SD	2.052	1.736		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 10, the values of $\bar{x}=11.13$ for first experimental group and $\bar{x}=8.18$ control group. The tabular t value 1.9873* is smaller than calculated value of t 7.378, depicted that there was prominent difference between the performance of first experimental group and control groups in the subject of chemistry.

Table 12

Comparison of overall post-test mean scores of the Control Group and the first Experimental group (N=90)

Groups	First Experimental Group	Control Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	23.88	17.35	88	8.893**
SD	4.02	2.84		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 12, the values of $\bar{x}=23.88$ for first experimental group and $\bar{x}=17.35$ for control group. The tabulated t value 1.9873* was very smaller than calculated t value 8.893**. These values are analyzed overall in both subjects of chemistry and mathematics from the prescribed topics. As compared to analysis given in Table 3, showed that the calculated value of t 0.589 was smaller than 1.9873 at a significance of the level of 0.05. Enhanced performance of same students of first experimental group (overall) was better due to the independent variable and intervention of teaching chemistry alongside mathematics. May be it is due to mutual relationship of concepts and principles of mathematics used in Chemistry.

Table 13

Comparison of Post-test mean scores of the Control Group and the second Experimental Group in the subject of Mathematics (N=90)

Groups	Second Experimental Group	Control Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	10.82	9.76	88	2.129**
SD	2.716	1.979		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 13, the values of $\bar{x}=10.82$ (second experimental group) and $\bar{x}=9.76$ (control group), it was found that there was a statistically significant difference between the above two groups concerning post-test mean scores.

Table 14

Comparison of Post-test mean scores of the Control Group and the second Experimental Group in the subject of Chemistry (N=90)

Groups	Second Experimental Group	Control Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	9.71	8.18	88	3.914**
SD	1.973	1.736		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 14, the values of $\bar{x}=9.71$ for second experimental group and $\bar{x}=8.18$ for control group. It was found that there is a statistically significant difference between the above two groups concerning post-test mean scores in the subject of Chemistry.

Table 15

Comparison of overall post-test mean scores of the Control Group and the second Experimental group (N=90)

Groups	Second Experimental Group	Control Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	20.57	17.35	88	4.211**
SD	4.27	2.84		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 15, the values of $\bar{x}=20.57$ for second experimental group and $\bar{x}=17.35$ for control group. It was found that there is a statistically significant difference between the above two groups concerning post-test mean scores. The result drawn is that the post-test performance of the Experimental groups was found better than the control group.

Table 16

Comparison of Performance of first Experimental Group and second Experimental Group on Post-test in Mathematics (N=90)

Groups	First Experimental Group	Second Experimental Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	12.00	10.82	88	2.381**
SD	1.907	2.716		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 16, the values of $\bar{x}=12.00$ (first experimental group) and $\bar{x}=10.82$ (second experimental group), it was found that there is a statistically significant difference between the above two groups concerning post-test mean scores in the subject of Mathematics. The result drawn is that the post-test performance of the Experimental groups was found better than the control group.

Table 17

Comparison of Performance of first Experimental Group and second Experimental Group on Post-test in Chemistry (N=90)

Groups	First Experimental Group	Second Experimental Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	11.13	9.71	88	3.352**
SD	2.052	1.973		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

As given in table 17, the values of $\bar{x}=11.13$ for first experimental group and $\bar{x}=9.71$ for second experimental group. Further tabulated value of t 1.9873* is smaller than the calculated value of t 3.914** but not too much significant shows that difference in performances of first experimental group and second experimental group exists. This minor difference may be due to the treatment of mathematics frequently before the class of chemistry and other one intervention of mathematics one week before the intervention of mathematics. Comparison of both experimental groups became interesting for researchers that variation in intervention may leads to variation in results.

Table 18

Comparison of Performance of First Experimental Group and Second Experimental Group on Post-test as a Whole test (overall) (N=90)

Groups	First Experimental Group	Second Experimental Group	df	t
N	45	45		1.9873*
M	23.88	20.57	88	3.780**
SD	4.029	4.277		

*table value **calculated at 0.05 significant level

In table 18 overall comparisons of post tests in mathematics and chemistry between first experimental group and second experimental groups was done. It appeared that the mean score on the post-test of the first experimental was 23.88 and that of the second experimental group was 20.57. As compared to analyses in table 17 almost the difference lie at the same level in table 18. Tabulated t value 1.9873* is smaller than calculated value 3.780**. Therefore, the performance of experimental group I (overall) could be treated as better due to the independent variable. This minor difference between first experimental group and second experimental group in table 16, 17 & 18 may be due to the treatment of mathematics frequently before the class of chemistry and other one intervention of mathematics one week before the intervention of mathematics. Comparison of both experimental groups became interesting for researchers that variation in intervention may leads to variation in results.

Results

1. Mean scores of the control group and the first experimental group were compared on the pre-test in the subject of Mathematics. Means scores of both groups were almost same and it was found that there was no statistically significant difference between the above two groups regarding pre-test mean scores. The result drawn is that the pre-test performance of both groups is almost at the same level in the subject of Mathematics (Table 1).
 2. As given in table 2, the values of $\bar{x}=3.36$ for first experimental group and $\bar{x}=3.42$ for control group showed no statistically significant difference between the above two groups concerning pre-test mean scores. Further tabulated t value 1.9873* was greater than calculated value 0.188** also depicted that there was no difference between the performance of first experimental group and control group in the subject of chemistry. The result drawn is that the pre-test performance of both groups is almost at the same level in the subject of Chemistry (Table 2).
 3. Analysis was done for overall performance of first experimental group and control group on pretest in both subjects of Mathematics and Chemistry. As given in table 3, $\bar{x}=9.20$ for first experimental group and $\bar{x}=9.56$ for control group on the pre test in both subjects of chemistry and mathematics was almost same. Further tabulate t value 1.9873* was less than calculated t value 0.589** showed that there was no statistically significant difference between the above two groups concerning pre-test mean scores in both the subjects (Table 3).
 4. Analysis of mean score and t values was done between second experimental group and control group on pretest in the subject of Mathematics. As given in the table mean value of second experimental group on the pretest in the subject of Mathematics was 5.31 and that of control group was 5.27, showing that both mean score values were almost same. In the same way calculated t value (0.107**) was also less than tabulated t value (1.9873**) resulted that there was no significant difference between the performance of the control group and second experimental group on pre-test in the subject of Mathematics (Table 4)
 5. Analysis of mean score and t values was done between second experimental group and control group on pretest in the subject of Chemistry. As given in the table mean value of second experimental group on the pretest in the subject of Chemistry was 3.47 and that of control group was 3.42, showing that both mean score values were almost same. In the same way calculated t value (0.120**) was also less than tabulated t value (1.9873**) resulted that there was no significant difference between the performance of the control group and second experimental group on pre-test in the subject of Chemistry (Table 5)
 6. As given in table 6, the values of $\bar{x}=9.09$ for second experimental group and $\bar{x}=9.56$ for control group showed that there was minor difference in mean scores on pre-test in both subjects of Mathematics and Chemistry. The result drawn is that the pre-test performance of both groups is almost at the same level. Table 6 shows that the calculated value of t (0.901) < (1.9873) at a significance of the level of 0.05. It means that there was no significant difference between the performance of the control group and second experimental group on the pre-test in both the subjects of Mathematics and Chemistry.
 7. Comparison between first experimental group and second experimental groups was done on pre test in the subject of Mathematics. The values of $\bar{x}=5.84$ for first experimental group and $\bar{x}=5.31$ for second experimental group showed minor difference. Further Table 7 shows that the calculated value of t (1.150*) < (1.9873) at a significance of the level of 0.05., it was found that there is no statistically significant difference between the above two groups concerning pre-test mean scores in the subject of Mathematics. The result drawn is that the pre-test performance of both groups is almost at the same level.
 8. Comparison between first experimental group and second experimental groups was done on pre test in the subject of Chemistry. The values of $\bar{x}=3.36$ for first experimental group and $\bar{x}=3.47$ for second experimental group showed minor difference. Further Table 8 shows that the calculated value of t (.313**) < (1.9873) at a significance of the level of 0.05, it was found that there is no statistically significant difference between the above two groups concerning pre-test mean scores in the subject of Chemistry. The result drawn is that the pre-test performance of both groups is almost at the same level.(Table 8)
- Note: Results of table 7 and table 8 on mean scores and t-values determined that the subject of Chemistry was difficult. We will see the results on posttest whether Mathematical principles helped students raising their means scores or not. Same can be inferred from table 1 & 2.
9. Comparison between first experimental group and second experimental groups was done on pre- test in the subject of Mathematics and Chemistry. The values of $\bar{x}=9.20$ for first experimental group and $\bar{x}=9.09$ for second experimental group resulted minor difference. Further Table 9 shows that the calculated value of t (0.187**) < (1.9873) at a significance of the level of 0.05, it was found that there is no statistically significant difference between the above two groups concerning pre-test mean scores in the subject of Mathematics and Chemistry. The result drawn is that the pre-test performance of both groups is almost at the same level.(Table 9)
 10. Comparison between first experimental group and control group on post test in the subject of Mathematics was done by using t-test. The values of $\bar{x}=12.0$ for first experimental group and

$\bar{x} = 9.76$ for control group showed that there was a prominent difference between mean score on posttest in the subject of Mathematics. The result drawn is that the post -test performance of both groups was at significant difference level. Table 10 showed that the calculated value of $t (5.479^{**}) > (1.9873^*)$ at a significance of the level of 0.05. Resultantly the performance of first experimental group was better than control group on posttest in the subject of Mathematics (Table10).

11. Comparison between first experimental group and control group on post test in the subject of Mathematics was done by using t-test. The values of $\bar{x} = 11.13$ for first experimental group and $\bar{x} = 8.18$ for control group showed, prominent difference between mean score on posttest in the subject of Mathematics. Table 11 showed that the calculated value of $t (7.378^{**}) > (1.9873^*)$ at a significance of the level of 0.05. Resultantly the performance of first experimental group was better than control group on posttest in the subject of Mathematics (Table11).
12. The results of comparison on posttest in both subjects of Mathematics and Chemistry between first experimental group and control group showed that performance of first experimental group was much better than that of control group. The results depicted that this enhanced overall performance was the result of teaching Chemistry alongside teaching of Mathematics. (Table 12)
13. The results of comparison on posttest in the subject of Mathematics between second experimental group and control group showed that performance of second experimental group was much better than that of control group. The results depicted that this enhanced overall performance was the result of teaching Mathematics alongside teaching of Chemistry (Table 13)
14. The results of comparison on posttest in the subject of Chemistry between second experimental group and control group showed that performance of second experimental group was much better than that of control group. The results depicted that this enhanced overall performance was the result of teaching Chemistry alongside teaching of Mathematics. (Table 14)
15. The results of comparison on posttest in both subjects of Mathematics and Chemistry between second experimental group and control group showed that performance of first experimental group was much better than that of control group. The results depicted that this enhanced overall performance was the result of teaching Chemistry alongside teaching of Mathematics and there might be a relationship among concepts of mathematics which help the learning Chemistry (Table 15)
16. The result drawn from comparison of first experimental group and second experimental group on the post-test was different at minute level in the subject of Mathematics. This may be due to the reason that mathematics was taught in two different format to enhance the understanding of Chemistry (Table 18)
17. Result from comparison of first experimental group and second experimental group on posttest in the subject of Chemistry showed minute significant shows that difference in performances of first experimental group and second experimental group exists. This minor difference may be due to the treatment of mathematics frequently before the class of chemistry and other one intervention of mathematics one week before the intervention of mathematics. Comparison of both experimental groups became interesting for researchers that variation in intervention may leads to variation in results.
18. Results drawn from the comparison of post tests in both subjects of Mathematics and Chemistry between first experimental group and second experimental groups was that there existed minor difference in performances of both groups. The performance of experimental group I (overall) could be treated as better due to the independent variable. This minor difference between first experimental group and second experimental group in table 16, 17 & 18 may be due to the treatment of mathematics frequently before the class of chemistry and other one intervention of mathematics one week before the intervention of mathematics. Comparison of both experimental groups became interesting for researchers that variation in intervention may leads to variation in results.

Conclusions

The performance of experimental group I and the control group was not significantly different on the pre-test in Mathematics. Hence, they were equal in Mathematics. The performance of experimental group I and control group was not significantly different on pre-test in Chemistry. Hence, they were equal in Chemistry. The performance of experimental group I and the control group was not significantly different on the pre-test as a whole (overall). Hence, they were equal as a whole (overall). There was no significant difference in the performance of the experimental II and control group on pre-test in Mathematics. Hence both groups are equal in Mathematics. There was no significant difference in the performance of experimental group II and control group on pre-test in Chemistry. Hence both groups are equal in Chemistry. There was no significant difference in the performance of the experimental II and control group on the pre-test as a whole (overall). Hence both groups are equal as a whole (overall). There was no significant difference in the performance of experimental groups I and II on pre-test in Mathematics. Hence they are equal in Mathematics. There was no significant change in the performance of experimental groups I and II on pre-test in Chemistry. Hence they are equal in Chemistry. There was no significant difference in the performance of experimental groups I and II on the pre-

test as a whole (overall). Hence they are equal as a whole (overall). There was a significant change in the performance of experimental group-I and control group on post-test as a whole (overall). It is concluded that teaching Mathematics before the teaching of Chemistry is effective. There was a significant difference in the performance of experimental group-II and control group on post-test as a whole (overall). It indicates that teaching Mathematics and Chemistry simultaneously is also effective. There was a significant difference in the performance of experimental group-I and experimental group-II on post-test as a whole (overall). It can be concluded that teaching relevant basic Mathematics principles before the teaching of Chemistry is more effective than the teaching of Mathematics, Chemistry simultaneously, and teaching of Chemistry by traditional method.

However, it is recommended that efforts may be made to sequence (in a specific order) teaching of Mathematics principles applicable in Chemistry and even in other science subjects in a manner that learners could apply knowledge and skills of Mathematics in solving Chemistry problems. Chemistry and Mathematics teachers may be trained to coordinate for required teaching. Further research may be conducted on other science subjects to find the effect of Mathematics on teaching.

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